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INVIGORATING THE 21ST CENTURY SKILLS IN BASIC EDUCATION: EQUIPPING PLAN

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Abstract: This research assessed the teacher's demonstration in line with 21st century skills at the identified schools in Lapu-Lapu city division in the School Year 2020-2021 as basis for development plan. The researchers used the descriptive research method to gather information about the respondents' demographic profile. The data obtained were analyzed using percentage weighted mean, standard deviation and t-test for significant difference with 0.05 level of significance. Results shows that teacher's response on their level of competence puts a challenging role to educators at present. Based on the findings, data shows that teachers have possessed the 21st century skills that helps them in providing quality education. Although, the data suggests that not all the 21st skills were rated high, still teachers possessed the basic knowledge in terms of embracing the new sets of skills in this new era. Further, finding shows that policymakers should sets some policy to elevated teachers 21st century skills to meet the global demands of education. Results also suggest that there is a need an immediate need of upgrading IT infrastructure and furthering research initiatives in every school especially during this time of pandemic. It is recommended that the proposed strategic plan crafted shall be considered for implementation.

Keywords: 21st Century Skills, Basic Education, Equipping Plan, Information and Media Literacy Skills

1. Introduction

Education plays a very important role in the development and progress of a certain nation. With the advancement of science and technology, it is indeed that globalization and internalization of education are considered as challenges that every country must uphold (Saldo et al., 2020). And one of the emphases of today's challenges in education is the promotion of 21st-century skills. In addition, education is a long-term investment in the labor force (Kuzminov et al., 2019; Novakova, 2020). Thus, its development has considerable economic benefits. Contemporary work requires high-level knowledge and skills, e.g., communication, critical thinking, and productive thinking (Trilling & Fadel, 2009). The concept of 21st century skills is used

to define what students should know and do to join the labor market and make decisions (Aleid, 2019).

According to Scott (2015) 21st century skills are the basic competencies and skills of successful life and work, e.g., communication, cooperation, critical thinking, and creativity taught in the context of 21st century topics. Kayange and Msiska (2016) report that 21st century skills are the skills required by students to participate effectively and successfully, acquire knowledge, master communication, and handle information effectively and efficiently to keep pace with the latest updates. Specialists argue that all students should master these skills.

Metz (2011) classifies 21st century skills into flexibility, adaptability, innovation, critical thinking, creativity, non-routine problem solving, complex communication, collaboration, social, and cross-cultural skills. According to Rotherham and Willingham (2009), 21st century skills include communication, digital literacy, thinking and problem solving, as well as personal and self-directional skills. Moreover, Higgins (2008) classified them into four groups, namely digital and electronic culture, creative thinking, effective communication, and high productivity. Generally, 21st century skills include critical, systematic, creativity, and logical thinking. They also include knowledge survey, teamwork, communication and adaptability, self-directional, social responsibility, global awareness, metacognition, technology, and problem identification and solution. Hofny (2015) categorized 21st century skills into learning (creative thinking, critical thinking, and communication) skills, knowledge (information awareness, media literacy, and technological knowledge) skills, and life skills.

Moreover, the Educational Laboratory North Central Regional (NCREL, 2003) classifies 21st century skills into four basic groups, namely digital age literacy (basic, scientific, economic, technological, visual and information, multicultural literacy and global awareness literacies) inventive thinking (adaptability, managing complexity, self-direction, curiosity, creativity, risk-taking, higher-order thinking, and sound reasoning), effective communication (teaming, collaboration, personal, social, civic responsibility, and interactive communication), and high productivity (prioritizing, planning, managing for results, effective use of real world tools, and ability to produce relevant and high-quality products).

Meanwhile, European Union Frame explores the competence and skills of long-life learning by conducting field studies in many countries to measure these skills. Jerald (2009) categorizes them into the emotional domain (strategies and motivation for learning, attitude to change, self-esteem, and learning environment), the cognitive domain (making and testing suggestions, using and testing rules, and using mental tools), and the meta-cognitive domain (problem solving, accuracy, and trusting the metacognition). The Frame of Arab League Educational, Cultural and Scientific Organization (ALECSO, (2014) divides 21st century skills into three main fields, namely advanced thinking skills (critical and analytical thinking, problem solving, creative thinking, and verbal intelligence), personal skills (communication, teamwork, cooperation, leadership, decision making, adjustment, self-management, self-confidence, work ethics, motivation to work, positivity, and estimating variation in the

work environment), and information technology (digital literacy, printing, using the internet, using Microsoft office, computer literacy, and mass media literacy). Other organizations have also developed frames for 21st century skills in education.

According to Shalabi (2014) the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) developed a framework in 2005 that included using tools interactively, with different groups, and acting independently. The aforementioned frameworks show a strong agreement on 21st century skills, but the organizations differ in terms of organizing these skills. Moreover, there is no uniquely defined inventory of these skills because of the different learning objectives that the organizations seek to achieve.

The job of school has changed to develop students, including the development of curiosity, understanding, and concluding facts independently. Therefore, several Arab workshops and conferences were held to discuss teacher's roles and 21st century skills required, such as the Third Conference on Information Technology Applications in Education in 2002 at Ege University, the Conference on Teacher Preparation for the Millennium and the Requirements of the Development Plan in Kuwait in 2003, the Conference on Teacher Preparation for the Third Millennium at the United Arab Emirates University in 2003, and the 2004 Conference on Globalization and Education Priorities at King Saud University (Alharby, 2013). Teacher preparation according to 21st century skills is an important developmental issue. These skills help students learn and achieve higher levels of education and help teachers develop. Kayange and Msiska (2016) emphasizes to include these skills entirely in education. Alharby (2013) identifies these 21st century skills as higher-order thinking, evaluation system management, knowledge economy support, and student abilities' management. Teachers have to include 21st century skills in classroom instruction to trigger student interaction with content and other students. They also have to master the use of technological devices and software in the classroom Hammond (2005). Shalabi (2014) argues that a teacher should master digital age literacy, inventive thinking, effective communication, and high productivity skills. Therefore, teacher preparation institutions should reconsider their programs to meet 21st century skills. Hofny (2015) argues that they should reconsider the content that can include a broader cognitive base and interdisciplinary topics in the various fields; skills that can cover learning and innovation, information and technology, and life and work; tools that help achieve these skills; occupational considerations that include psychological, educational, and technological considerations, such as teacher attitudes and motivation and optimal use of technology when designing instruction.

The Philippines is in the midst of tremendous change in education and in the verge of still greater ones. Education today is different from what it was ten or fifteen years ago, and it will be more difficult as people carry on their tasks in providing the culture of learning and quality education. The teaching profession is a challenging vocation that calls for highly skilled and performing individuals. The intricacies of the work coupled with the demanding needs of the times have posed challenges to the teachers. The new teaching paradigm of DepEd on international, national and local competitiveness is the implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program to all

public elementary and secondary schools in the Philippines by President Aquino III. This curricular reform has developed a framework which aims for the holistic development of the learners and opened the way to the mandated 21st Century Skills (K- 12 Basic Education Program, 2012). These include teachers' minimum level of competencies in Learning and Innovation Skills; Information, Media and Technology Skills; and Life and Career Skills. This is a breakthrough in the field of education which is tantamount to redirection of skills and competencies of teachers. Such competencies will take a pivotal role in gauging job performance which is one of the indicators if education has met certain level of standards. Performance is equated with quality and excellence (Pa-alisbo, 2017). And to cope with these challenges given by the changing world and knowledge economy, alternatives were presented and implemented by the countries around the world to help individuals attain education through nonformal and informal education (Colardyn & Bjornavold, 2004), especially in developing countries (Nath, Sylvia, & Grimes, 1999) such as the Philippines. The Philippines is active in accepting the global challenge of providing Educational Services to the Filipinos. In fact, in the year 1990, the international development community birthed a massive global education initiative called Education for All (EFA) 2015 (Gonzales, 1999). The Philippine government has adopted this commitment of EFA goals in EFA assembly in Jomtien, Thailand, in 1990 and Dakar, Bangladesh, in 2000. The country also adapts Millennium Development Goals (MDG) in 2001 and the Decade for Literacy in 2003. But despite this educational goal, the country still continuously suffers a very high dropouts statistically 62% of the Filipino Student Population or 11,000,000 in total (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, 2010). The Government efforts to combat school attrition through strengthening student programs and developing a system that will promote continuing education, thus, promulgated Republic Act 9155 in 2001 or the Governance Act of Basic Education which provides provisions that will address illiteracy and promote continuing education.

Education in Philippines can benefit from the expertise of other developed countries in teacher preparation according to the 21st century skills by integrating 21st century into the curriculum. New methods of organizing education according to the needs of the students and the community shall be developed by reviewing the perspective of experts to highlight shortcomings in the existing curricula and developing a comprehensive system that meets 21st century skills. Pre-service teacher preparation shall be carried out in learning environments that meet the 21st century like the case of Finland. Furthermore, focus on learning should not be limited to the contents of the curriculum. Rather, the contents are tools to achieve the skills by arranging learning contexts and real environments. Training units can be established in public schools to use technology in the classroom and enable teachers to manage classrooms and handle modern skills. National standards of technology use in teacher preparation are developed to promote teachers' cognitive capabilities, meet the needs of education, and express creative ideas. Additionally, a set of quality standards of teacher professional development shall be considered to prepare 21st century teachers.

2. Purpose of the Study

This research assessed the status of teachers teaching-learning in line with the 21st century skills. The level of teacher's demonstration of the 21st century skills of the following aspects: Information and media literacy skills, communication skills Understanding, critical thinking and systems thinking, problem identification, formulation, and solution, creativity and intellectual curiosity, interpersonal and collaborative skills, self-direction skills, accountability and adaptability, social Responsibility were considered in the main problem of the study.

3. Research Methodology

The descriptive method of research was used in this study, which described data and the characteristics of the population under study. Together with sets of questionnaires as data gathering instruments. As widely used, descriptive research describes a certain present state. Reasonably, the method is applicable to this study since it aims to describe the current condition. This method answered the questions who, what, where, when, and how. In particular, the present conditions of the respondents as regards to the need of the teachers in line with 21st Century skills. The data gathered were treated by the aid of statistical software utilizing 0.05 level of significance. Teachers and administrators were the main respondents of the study. The main instrument of the study was adapted from the study of Alhothali (2021) it highlights the differences in the reality of including 21st century skills of teachers.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Information and Media Literacy Skills

Information and media literacy skills	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Teachers has the ability to use technology creatively and effectively in various learning environments.	4.00	A	3.75	A
Teachers are qualified for new functions under fast technology development.	3.33	MA	3.15	MA
Teachers are trained in cooperation, communication, and critical thinking using modern means of technology	3.33	MA	3.55	A
Teachers are trained in accessing and managing information.	3.67	A	3.55	MA
Teachers are trained in the evaluation and analysis of information	3.38	MA	3.40	MA
Grand Mean	3.54	A	3.48	A

Table 1 shows the data on in Information and media literacy skills. Data shows that teachers who has the ability to use technology creatively and effectively in various learning environments got the highest weighted mean of 4.00 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to teachers who were qualified for new functions under fast technology development and trained in cooperation, communication, and critical thinking using modern means of technology got the lowest weighted mean of 3.33 which describes as moderately agree. On the other hand, administrators' response also agreed that teachers have the ability to use technology creatively and effectively in various learning environment at 3.75 mean while statement refers to teachers are qualified for new functions under fast technology development. Previous research shows that media literacy education is to empower your students with the tools to

communicate and thrive successfully in society. Teachers need to consider the current literacy demands of the technological age. Teachers are ultimately responsible to teach your students to communicate. While reading and writing are the heart and soul of standard literacy education, you should reconsider what it means to be literate in this technological age. Through media literacy, students benefit from learning in ways that allow them to participate fully in public, community, and economic life (PDA, 2019).

Table 2. Communication Skills

Communication skills	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Teachers has interpersonal skills and reading and writing components successfully	3.36	MA	3.80	A
Teachers are trained in understanding, managing, and creating effective communication orally and in writing using multimedia	3.43	A	3.46	A
The teacher is trained in processing and discussing verbal and non-verbal information.	3.20	MA	3.60	A
Teachers are trained on the ability to define basic points to be expressed verbally and nonverbally.	4.00	A	3.45	A
The teacher is trained in using mass media and several techniques to broaden communication.	3.43	MA	3.42	A
Grand Mean	3.48	A	3.55	A

Table 2 shows the data on communication skills. Data shows that teachers are trained on the ability to define basic points to be expressed verbally and nonverbally got the highest weighted mean of 4.00 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to teacher is trained in processing and discussing verbal and non-verbal information got the lowest weighted mean of 3.20, which verbally described as moderately agree. Administrators' response on the other hand, the statement refers to teachers has interpersonal skills and reading and writing components successfully was rated as agree with a weighted mean of agree, while the statement refers to the teacher is trained in using mass media and several techniques to broaden communication got the lowest weighted mean of 3.42, which also verbally described as agree. Overall, teachers and administrator rated agree in terms of communication skills.

Table 3. Critical Thinking and Systems Thinking Skills

Critical thinking and systems thinking skills	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The department of education provide the ability to use higher-order thinking skills effectively for planning, instruction, and thinking in educational practices.	4.10	A	3.43	A
The teacher is trained in understanding the correlation between the systems	3.23	MA	3.25	MA
The teacher is trained in thinking about the learned concepts.	3.30	MA	3.15	MA
The department of education promote the application of the learned concepts.	3.67	A	3.55	A
The teacher is trained in making complex choices.	3.13	MA	3.42	A
Grand Mean	3.49	A	3.36	MA

Table 3 shows the data on critical thinking and system thinking skills. Data shows that statement refers to department of education provide the ability to use higher-order thinking skills effectively for planning, instruction, and thinking in educational practices got the highest weighted mean of 4.10 which verbally described as agree,

while the statement refers to the teacher is trained in making complex choices got the lowest weighted mean of 3.13 which verbally described as moderately agree. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to the department of education promote the application of the learned concepts got the highest weighted mean of 3.55, while the statement refers to teacher is trained in thinking about the learned concepts got the lowest weighted mean of 3.15 which verbally described as moderately agree. This entails that there is a need for teacher need to trained themselves in thinking the recent trend and concepts in education. Overall, teachers rated critical thinking and system thinking skills with a weighted mean of 3.49 which verbally described as agree, while administrator rated teachers critical thinking and system thinking skills as moderately agree. This indicates that there is a need to re program the way teachers think in the advent of education 4.0 in line with 21st century skills.

Table 4. Problem Identification, Formulation, and Solution Skills

Problem identification, formulation, and solution skills	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The department of education equip the teacher with the ability to solve problems using an adequate method.	4.20	A	3.75	A
The teacher is trained in the ability to contextualize.	3.28	MA	3.15	MA
The teacher is trained in logical analysis to solve problems.	3.32	MA	3.87	A
The teacher is trained in design and choosing the appropriate evidence.	3.67	A	4.08	MA
The department of education focus on finding, analyzing, and using the information to solve problems.	3.26	MA	3.42	A
Grand Mean	3.55	A	3.65	A

Table 4 shows the data on problem identification, formulation, and solution skills. Data shows that statement refers to the department of education equip the teacher with the ability to solve problems using an adequate method got the highest weighted mean of 4.20 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to the department of education focus on finding, analyzing, and using the information to solve problems got the lowest weighted mean of 3.26 which verbally described as moderately agree. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to the teacher is trained in design and choosing the appropriate evidence. got the highest weighted mean of 4.08, while the statement refers to the teacher is trained in the ability to contextualize got the lowest weighted mean of 3.15 which verbally described as moderately agree. This entails that their teacher is trained in solving problem relevant to 21st century skills. Overall, teachers rated problem identification, formulation, and solution skills with a weighted mean of 3.55 which verbally described as agree, while administrator rated teacher's problem identification, formulation, and solution skills with a weighted mean of 3.65 which also verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that teachers and administrators agreed that teacher themselves have the skills in solving problem relevant to new trend in education and society.

Table 5 shows the data on creativity and intellectual curiosity. Data shows that statement refers to the department of education focus on supporting the teacher in applying theories to real situations got the highest weighted mean of 4.10 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to the teacher is trained in

implementing new and creative ideas got the lowest weighted mean of 3.26 which verbally described as moderately agree

Table 5. Creativity and intellectual curiosity

Creativity and intellectual curiosity	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The department of education focus on supporting the teacher in applying theories to real situations.	4.10	A	4.02	A
The teacher is trained in implementing new and creative ideas.	3.26	MA	3.12	MA
The teacher is trained in using higher-order thinking skills effectively for planning, teaching, and thinking about teaching practices.	3.42	A	3.68	A
The department of education play a part in the development and creation of new ideas.	3.57	A	4.02	MA
The department of education focus on supporting the teacher in sharing new ideas with others.	3.28	MA	3.48	A
Grand Mean	3.53	A	3.66	A

Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to the department of education focus on supporting the teacher in applying theories to real situations and the department of education play a part in the development and creation of new ideas got the highest weighted mean of 4.02, while the statement refers to the teacher is trained in implementing new and creative ideas got the lowest weighted mean of 3.15 which verbally described as moderately agree. Overall, teachers rated creativity and intellectual curiosity with a weighted mean of 3.53 which verbally described as agree, while administrator rated teacher's creativity and intellectual curiosity with a weighted mean of 3.66 which also verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers and administrators agreed that teacher were creative and have intellectual curiosity like a scientist in a new era.

Table 6. Interpersonal and collaborative skills

Interpersonal and collaborative skills	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Teachers are trained in adjusting to various roles and responsibilities.	4.00	A	3.80	A
Teachers are trained in taking responsibility.	4.00	A	3.70	A
The programs focus on supporting teachers to work effectively in various teams.	3.67	A	3.60	A
The department of education promote sympathy and respecting other opinions.	3.62	A	3.40	A
The teacher is trained in efficient interaction with others.	3.00	MA	3.50	A
The department of education focus on supporting the teacher in fruitful teamwork.	4.33	SA	3.85	A
Weighted Mean	3.77	A	3.64	A

Table 6 shows the data on interpersonal and collaborative skills. Data shows that statement refers to department of education focus on supporting the teacher in fruitful teamwork. got the highest weighted mean of 4.33 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to the teacher is trained in efficient interaction with others. got the lowest weighted mean of 3.00 which verbally described as moderately

agree. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to the department of education focus on supporting the teacher in fruitful teamwork. got the highest weighted mean of 3.85 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to department of education promote sympathy and respecting other opinions. got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as agree. Overall, teachers rated interpersonal and collaborative skills with a weighted mean of 3.77 which verbally described as agree, while administrator rated teacher's interpersonal and collaborative skills with a weighted mean of 3.64 which also verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers and administrators agreed that teacher have interpersonal and collaborative skills that they can use to provide quality education.

Table 7. Self-Direction Skills

Self-direction skills	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The teacher is trained in developing self-learning skills.	3.36	MA	3.75	A
The teacher is trained in monitoring personal understanding and learning needs.	4.00	A	3.50	A
The teacher is trained in transferring learning from a field to another.	3.35	MA	3.90	A
The teacher is trained in time and goal management.	4.00	A	3.55	A
The department of education focus on supporting the teacher in defining resources.	3.00	MA	3.20	MA
Weighted Mean	3.54	A	3.58	A

Table 7 shows the data on teacher's self-direction skills. Data shows that statement refers to the teacher is trained in monitoring personal understanding and learning needs and the teacher is trained in time and goal management got the highest weighted mean of 4.00 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to the department of education focus on supporting the teacher in defining resources got the lowest weighted mean of 3.00 which verbally described as moderately agree. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to the teacher is trained in transferring learning from a field to another got the highest weighted mean of 3.90 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to the department of education focus on supporting the teacher in defining resource got the lowest weighted mean of 3.58 which verbally described as agree. Overall, teachers rated self-direction skills with a weighted mean of 3.54 which verbally described as agree, while administrator rated teacher's self-direction skills with a weighted mean of 3.58 which also verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers and administrators agreed that teacher have self-direction skills that they can use to help students in achieving their dreams in life.

Table 8 shows the data on teacher's accountability and adaptability skills. Data shows that statement refers to the teacher is provided with a strategy to develop and meet higher standards and objectives and the teacher is provided with a strategy to develop and meet higher standards and objectives got the highest weighted mean of 4.00 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to the teacher is trained in ethical work and collaboration with workmates and the teacher is trained in prioritizing needs and time management. got the lowest weighted mean of 3.33 which verbally described as moderately agree.

Table 8. Accountability and adaptability skills

Accountability and adaptability skills	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The teacher is trained in project management, as well as prioritizing, planning, and managing work	4.00	A	3.45	A
The teacher is trained in ethical work and collaboration with workmates.	3.33	MA	3.40	A
The teacher is provided with a strategy to develop and meet higher standards and objectives.	4.00	A	3.65	A
The teacher is trained in prioritizing needs and time management.	3.33	MA	3.60	A
The teacher is trained in personal responsibility and flexibility in personal contexts, workplaces, and society.	3.48	A	3.56	A
Weighted Mean	3.63	A	3.53	A

Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to the teacher is provided with a strategy to develop and meet higher standards and objectives got the highest weighted mean of 3.65 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers the teacher is trained in ethical work and collaboration with workmates got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as agree. Overall, teachers rated self-direction skills with a weighted mean of 3.63 which verbally described as agree, while administrator rated teacher's self-direction skills with a weighted mean of 3.53 which also verbally described as agree. This indicates that teachers and administrators agreed that teacher have accountability and adaptability skills that they can use to continually improved themselves in this new era.

Table 9. Social Responsibility Skills

Social responsibility skills	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The department of education focus on supporting the teacher to take more responsibility in the interests of society.	3.43	A	3.65	A
The department of education focus on supporting the teacher in using differences to develop new ideas and solutions for problems.	3.20	MA	3.10	MA
The teacher is trained in effective interaction with others and act politely and professionally.	3.67	A	3.40	A
The teacher is trained in ethical behavior in personal contexts, workplaces, and society.	3.10	MA	3.16	MA
The teacher is trained in respect and adopting sociocultural differences.	3.20	MA	3.48	A
Weighted Mean	3.32	MA	3.36	MA

Table 9 shows the data on teacher's social responsibility skills. Data shows that statement refers to department of education focus on supporting the teacher to take more responsibility in the interests of society got the highest weighted mean of 3.43 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers the teacher is trained in ethical behavior in personal contexts, workplaces, and society got the lowest weighted mean of 3.33 which verbally described as moderately agree. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to the teacher is trained in respect and adopting sociocultural

differences got the highest weighted mean of 3.65 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers the department of education focus on supporting the teacher in using differences to develop new ideas and solutions for problems got the lowest weighted mean of 3.10 which verbally described as moderately agree. Overall, teachers rated social responsibility skills with a weighted mean of 3.32 which verbally described as moderately agree, while administrator rated teacher's social responsibility skills with a weighted mean of 3.36 which also verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that teachers and administrators agreed that teacher need to develop their social responsibility skills in order to participate and contribute in our society not just only in school.

Table 10. Significant Mean Difference Between Respondent Group

Sources	21 st Century Skills	MEAN	p-value	Decision
Teachers	Information and media literacy skills	3.54	0.7158	Significant
		3.48		
Administrators	Communication skills Understanding	3.48	0.6958	Significant
		3.55		
	Critical thinking and systems thinking	3.49	0.5304	Significant
		3.36		
	Problem identification, formulation, and solution	3.55	0.6700	Significant
		3.65		
	Creativity and intellectual curiosity	3.53	0.5650	Significant
		3.66		
	Interpersonal and collaborative skills	3.77	0.535	Significant
3.64				
Self-direction skills	3.55	0.8733	Significant	
	3.58			
accountability and adaptability	3.63	0.5679	Significant	
	3.53			
Social Responsibility	3.32	0.7996	Significant	
	3.36			

The Table 10 described the significant differences of the teachers and administrators of teachers 21st century skills. Data shows that p value is greater than alpha 0.05, this indicates that there is enough evidence to prove that teachers and administrators do not differ much on its level of perception on teachers 21st century skills. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted that there is no significant different on the respondent groups perception.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings, data shows that teachers have possessed the 21st century skills that helps them in providing quality education. Although, the data suggests that not all the 21st skills were rated high, still teachers possessed the basic knowledge in terms of embracing the new sets of skills in this new era. Further, finding shows that policymakers should sets some policy to elevated teachers 21st century skills to meet the global demands of education. Results also suggest that there is a need an immediate need of upgrading IT infrastructure and furthering research initiatives in every school especially during this time of pandemic.

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